
Research Article

***Salmonella* and *Shigella* Assessment of Smoked Atlantic Horse Mackerel (*Trachurus trachurus*) and Blue Whiting (*Micromesistius poutasou*) Sold in Ilaro, Yewa-South, Nigeria**

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Abstract

Fresh fish is highly perishable and prone to microbial spoilage. Over the years, different techniques have been adopted for fish preservation, although post-processing contamination of smoked fish is still of great concern. Microbial quality of smoked Atlantic Horse Mackerel (*Trachurus trachurus*) and Blue Whiting (*Micromesistius poutasou*) sold in Ilaro was assessed for the presence of *Salmonella* and *Shigella* as parameter to determine the quality of the fish samples. A total of eighteen (18) fish samples were collected from three different marketing sites in Ilaro, Yewa-South, Nigeria. The Bacteriological analysis of the samples was carried out using pour plate technique. The Total viable count of Horse Mackerel from Orita (KO) ranged from 4.0×10^5 to 1.27×10^5 cfu/g. Horse Mackerel from Igboro (KI) had bacterial load ranged from 1.2×10^3 and 9.4×10^3 cfu/g. The bacterial load of Horse Mackerel from Gbogidi (KG) ranged from 4.6×10^2 to 6.0×10^3 cfu/g. There was no presence of *Salmonella* and *Shigella* in Horse Mackerel from the various marketing sites sampled. The bacterial load of Blue Whiting from Orita (PO) ranged from 4.4×10^2 to 1.6×10^3 cfu/g. Blue Whiting from Igboro (PI) had bacterial load, ranged from 4.4×10^2 to 1.63×10^3 cfu/g. The bacterial load of Blue Whiting from Gbogidi ranged from 4.6×10^2 to 6.0×10^3 cfu/g. All the fish samples were free of *Salmonella* and *Shigella* except sample PG₁. Although most of the fish samples obtained from the three markets sites are safe for human

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consumption, there is need for the smoking and storage methods to be improved on so as to prevent pre and post contaminations.

Key: Bacterial load, contamination, fish, marketing sites, safe.

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Introduction

Fish is an important protein source in the tropics, it represents about 14% of animal proteins consumed globally (Abolagba and Melle, 2008). Fish and fish products constitute over 60% of the total protein intake in adults especially in the rural areas of West Africa countries. More so, fish and fish products account for about 41% of animal proteins consumed in Nigeria (Rahji and Bada, 2010). For over two decades, demand for fishes in Nigeria has increased due to high cost of beef, increase in population and health benefits associated with fish and fish products. The health benefits of fish and fish products might be due to their high digestibility and polyunsaturated fatty acids. Fishes consumption in Nigeria does not have socio-economical, age, religious and educational barriers (Adebayo-Tayo *et al.*, 2008). Fish protein is a good source of lysine, methionine and tryptophan. It is also rich in zinc, phosphorus, iron and calcium. More so, high riboflavin, vitamins A and D are readily available in fish (Olaleye and Abegunde, 2015).

However, fish is highly perishable, quality deterioration might occur rapidly shortly after catching, especially in hot climates and tropical areas where cold preservation technique is often missing due to lack of stable electricity supply. The high protein and water contents of fish play important roles in quick spoilage of fish (Adeyemi *et al.*, 2013). There is a need for the fishes to be preserved in order to reduce economic losses. In tropical regions especially West Africa, traditional processes such as drying, salting, fermentation, smoking and combinations of these treatments are used for fish preservation (Anihouvi *et al.*, 2006). Smoking had been used for centuries in preserving fish, and it still remains the most popular method of fish processing (Bako, 2005).

Fishes are susceptible to wide variety of potential pathogenic bacteria (Schmidt *et al.*, 2000). *Salmonella* spp., *Staphylococcus* spp., *Escherichia coli*, *Vibrio parahaemolyticus*, *Clostridium perferenges* and Enteroviruses are mostly associated with fish related foodborne illness (Babalola *et al.*, 2011). Consumption of contaminated fish and fish

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products may induce disease and cause abdominal pain, acute gastroenteritis, bloody or mucoid diarrhea, nausea, vomiting and fever. Contamination of fish and fish products may come from water environment and post-harvest contamination. Presence of *Salmonella* and *Shigella* in fish and fish products is of public health concern.

Salmonella infection has long been of public concern (Brands, 2006). *Salmonella* is the most common contaminant of fish and fish products (Allshouse *et al.*, 2004) and causes public health problems. High percentage food poisoning outbreaks are associated with consumption of raw or insufficiently cooked fish and cross contamination of fish during processing, and about 12% of the foodborne outbreaks that are related to consumption of fish are caused by bacteria such as *Salmonella* (Huss *et al.*, 2000; Aberoumand, 2010). It has been known to cause health problem associated with consumption of fish and fish products. The presence of *Salmonella* in fish and fish product is a sign of poor standards of processing and sanitation. The bacterium is principally found in the gastrointestinal tracts of mammals, reptiles, birds, insects, and environment polluted with human and animal faeces (Saeed and Naji, 2007). Aquatic environments are the major reservoirs of *Salmonella*. Therefore, fishery products are recognized as major carrier of foodborne pathogens (Upsdhyay *et al.*, 2010).

Shigella is also similar to *Salmonella*. It's also one of the enterobacteria that are responsible for foodborne illnesses. *Shigella* is known to cause shigellosis (bacillary dysentery), that is characterized by fever, nausea, stomach upset, vomiting and severe diarrhea. Sea foods are responsible for a number of outbreaks of shigellosis (Novotny *et al.*, 2004), this might be due to contamination of raw fish or previously processed fish. The bacterium is found in the waste products of infected individual and can easily be transmitted (Upadhyay *et al.*, 2010). The presence of *Salmonella* and *Shigella* has been reported in fishes and other sea foods (Afolabi and Fabunmi, 2018; Ayeloja *et al.*, 2018). Horse Mackerel (*Trachurus trachurus*) and Blue Whiting (*Micromesistius poutasou*) are readily available imported fishes in most Nigeria markets. The fishes; Horse Mackerel and Blue Whiting are popularly known as Kote and Panla respectively in Yoruba speaking part of Nigeria. The availability of these fishes Ilaro markets is due to proximity to the numerous porous border routes. The fishes are usually processed to ready-to-eat smoked fish in order to increase shelf-life and add value. The study was to determine the bacterial loads of Atlantic Horse Mackerel (Kote) and Blue Whiting (Panla) sold in three marketing sites in Ilaro.

Materials and Methods

Collection of Samples

Smoked Blue Whiting; *Micromesistius poutasou* (Panla) and smoked Atlantic Horse Mackerel; *Trachurus trachurus* (Kote), were randomly sampled and purchased between November 2016 and January 2017, from three marketing sites. The marketing sites were Orita, Igboro and Gbogidi; all are located in Ilaro, Yewa-South local government of Ogun State. Each marketing site was sampled thrice, a total of nine (9) Kote and nine (9) Panla samples were purchased from different Vendors. The samples were subsequently kept in sterile polyethylene bags and transported within 1 h from sampling sites to the laboratory for bacterial analysis.

Bacteriological Analyses

Salmonella/Shigella agar and Plate count agar were used for the analysis. The media were prepared according to manufacturers' instructions. Pour plate technique was adopted for the bacteriological analyses. Each fish sample was aseptically removed from the sterile polyethylene bag and sterile forceps was used to remove the flesh with the skin. A ten-fold serial dilution was carried out in order to determine the bacterial load and the presence of *Salmonella* and *Shigella* in the fish samples. The inoculated plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 h. The total viable counts (TVC) were enumerated using colony counter. Pure isolates were preserved on agar slant and kept in the fridge before preliminary identification (Salaudeen *et al.*, 2010)

Identification of Isolates

The isolates obtained from Salmonella/Shigella plates were identified using conventional method as described by Salaudeen *et al.* (2010) and Ayeloja *et al.* (2018). The organisms were identified on the basis of their colonial morphology, cellular characteristics, and biochemical tests such as catalase test, indole test, citrate utilization test, sugar fermentation and oxidase test. Bergey's Manual of Determinative Bacteriology was consulted as reference for identification (Holt *et al.*, 1994).

Results and Discussion

Results

The mean bacterial loads of Horse Mackerel samples collected from the three marketing sites are shown in Table 1. The bacterial load of Horse Mackerel samples from Orita (KO) ranged from 4.0×10^5 to 1.27×10^5 cfu/g. Atlantic Horse Mackerel samples from

Table 1: Mean bacterial load of Horse Mackerel (Kote) Samples

Sample	Total Viable Count (Cfu/g)	<i>Salmonella</i> (Cfu/g)	<i>Shigella</i> (Cfu/g)
KO ₁	4.0x10 ²	NIL	NIL
KO ₂	4.5x10 ²	NIL	NIL
KO ₃	1.27x10 ⁵	NIL	NIL
KI ₁	1.2x10 ³	NIL	NIL
KI ₂	2.4x10 ³	NIL	NIL
KI ₃	9.4x10 ³	NIL	NIL
KG ₁	4.9x10 ²	NIL	NIL
KG ₂	1,2x10 ³	NIL	NIL
KG ₃	1.03x10 ⁵	NIL	NIL

KO: Kote Orita, KI: Kote Igboro, KG: Kote Gbogidi

Igboro (KI) had bacterial load ranged from 1.2x10³ to 9.4x10³cfu/g. The bacterial load of Atlantic Horse Mackerel from Gbogidi (KG) ranged from 4.6x10² to 6.0x10³cfu/g. From the Atlantic Horse Mackerel samples collected from Orita, KO₁ had the least bacterial load (4.0x10²cfu/g) while KO₃ had the highest bacterial load (1.27x10⁵cfu/g). Likewise, from Atlantic Horse Mackerel samples collected from Igboro, KI₁ had the least bacterial load (1.2x10³cfu/g) while KI₃ had the highest load (9.4x10³cfu/g). Among the Atlantic Horse Mackerel samples from Gbogidi, KG₂ had the least bacterial load (4.6x10²cfu/g) and KG₃ had the highest load (6.0x10³cfu/g). When compared to the bacterial load of the Atlantic Horse Mackerel samples from the three marketing sites, KO₃ had the highest bacterial load. There was no *Salmonella* and *Shigella* isolated from the Atlantic Horse Mackerel samples.

The results of bacterial load of Blue Whiting samples from the various sampled marketing sites are shown in Table 2. The bacterial load of Blue Whiting from Orita (PO) ranged from 4.4x10² to 1.6x10³cfu/g. Blue Whiting samples from Igboro (PI) had bacterial load ranged from 4.4x10² to 1.63x10³cfu/g. The bacterial load of Blue Whiting from Gbogidi ranged from 4.6x10² to 6.0x10³cfu/g. From Blue Whiting collected from Orita, PO₂ had the least bacterial load (4.4x10²cfu/g) while the highest bacterial load (1.6x10³cfu/g) was recorded in PO₁. From the results in Table 2, the least bacterial load (4.4x10²cfu/g) was recorded in PI₂ out Blue Whiting samples collected from Igboro while the highest bacterial load (1.6x10³cfu/g) was recorded in sample PI₁. In Blue Whiting samples collected from Gbogidi, PG₃ had the least bacterial load (4.6x10²cfu/g)

Table 2: Mean bacterial load of Blue Whiting (Panla) Samples

Sample	Total Viable Count (Cfu/g)	<i>Salmonella</i> (Cfu/g)	<i>Shigella</i> (Cfu/g)
PO ₁	1.6x10 ³	NIL	NIL
PO ₂	4.4x10 ²	NIL	NIL
PO ₃	6.6x10 ²	NIL	NIL
PI ₁	1.63x10 ³	NIL	NIL
PI ₂	4.41x10 ²	NIL	NIL
PI ₃	8.7x10 ²	NIL	NIL
PG ₁	6.0x10 ³	NIL	2.4x10 ³
PG ₂	2.0x10 ³	NIL	NIL
PG ₃	4.6x10 ²	NIL	NIL

PO: Panla Orita, PI: Panla Igboro, PG: Panla Gbogidi

while the highest bacterial load (6.0x10³cfu/g) was recorded in sample PG₁. When compared the bacterial load of the various Blue Whiting samples from the three marketing sites, PG₁ had the highest bacterial load. There was no *Salmonella* isolated from the Blue Whiting (Panla) samples while *Shigella* (2.4x10³cfu/g) was recorded in PG₁.

Discussion

Fishery products are important not only due to nutritional point of view, but could also boost international trade between a numbers of countries, and could be good source of foreign exchange. Fish and shellfish are highly perishable, and are prone to vast variation in quality due to differences in species, environmental habitats and feeding habits (Sanaa, 2009). Fish and fish product can be carriers of several bacterial that might be of public health concern. Nigeria markets are full of imported fishes whose microbial safety is not ascertained. Due to the perishable nature of fresh fish, market women usually preserve and add value to the fish by smoking drying them.

As observe in this study, the total viable count (TVC) of Kote and Panla samples collected from the three marketing sites were within acceptable standard. According to ICMSF (1986), the total viable count should be less than 10⁶cfu/g and the borderline limit of acceptable is between 10⁶ and less than 10⁷cfu/g. This study was in agreement with the work of Amusan *et al.* (2010), although the samples were not collected the same marketing sites, the similarity might be due similar or same source of the fresh fish

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since they are imported fishes. The results of total viable counts were in contrary to the work of Abisoye *et al.* (2011), the variation might be due to difference source of raw fish, difference environment and handling. The smoked fishes in Nigeria most times are openly displayed by the market women without taken into consideration microbial contamination from the environment (Akinwumi and Adegbehingbe, 2015).

All the Kote samples showed no *Salmonella* and *Shigella* growth, but a sample of Blue Whiting (Panla) assessed, showed presence *Shigella*. Absence of *Salmonella* and *Shigella* in the Atlantic Horse Mackerel (Kote) samples analysed was in agreement with the findings of Abisoye *et al.* (2011). Likewise, the absence of *Salmonella* in the Panla samples was in agreement with the studies of Amusan *et al.* (2010). The presence of *Shigella* in one of the Panla samples could be due to faecal contamination of the fresh fish or the smoked fish; this might be due to poor hygiene practice of the vendors or environment where the fishes are being sold. The presence of the organism could also be due to poor handling during smoking and cross contamination during storage or sales of the smoked fish. The fish could be source of *Shigella* infection (bacillary dysentery) that is of public health concern. More so, about 12% of the foodborne outbreaks that are related to consumption of fish are caused by bacteria such as *Shigella* (Huss *et al.*, 2000; Aberoumand, 2010).

Conclusions

The fish samples were not heavily contaminated with bacteria, the total viable counts of the samples were within acceptable limit. The presence of *Shigella* was recorded in Blue White (Panla) sample from Gbogidi makes it unsafe for human consumption. Although, from the results of this study, the hygienic practice of the vendors (market women) from the three marketing sites was okay, but there is still need to educate them regularly on the importance of good hygienic practice. Likewise, there is a need for the smoking and storage methods to be improved on so as to prevent pre and post contaminations.

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